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Title: Communicating Scientific Research: Introduction to a Case Study of Public Relations Implementation in the SynTrac Project

Abstract:

Over the past few decades, models of science communication have undergone significant transformation, driven by both societal demands and strategic policy shifts at national and European levels. Increasing investments in science communication, particularly on pressing topics such as climate change and the COVID-19 pandemic, reflect a growing awareness of its societal value. This recognition has led to additional institutional resources, including the establishment of dedicated public relations projects. Part of the supporting structures of the collaborative research council TRR 364 SynTrac (Synergies of Highly Integrated Transport Aircraft) is such a dedicated PR sub-project. The SynTrac consortium is researching the scientific basis for a vision of future, highly integrated aircraft that use less energy to achieve the same performance, thus producing fewer emissions. SynTrac's potential impact on climate change and its value to society firmly places its research agenda in the science communication arena.

But despite increasing awareness and resources, the field of science communication continues to grapple with persistent challenges, most notably in the area of evaluation, where the impact and efficacy of communication strategies remain difficult to measure systematically. This paper introduces a SynTrac case study, which exemplifies a contemporary, multi-channel science communication initiative. Combining analog and digital formats the project delivers tailored content for designated target groups and explores effective ways to evaluate the efficacy of the content. Outlining opportunities and challenges in developing a diverse communication and outreach portfolio and the accompanying evaluation strategy, the SynTrac study offers valuable insights into current practice and future directions for science communication.

Key words: Sustainable Aviation, Science Communication, Public Relations, Outreach, STEM, Research Project

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